

Isomeric and chemical consequences of the direct magnesiation of 1,3-benzoazoles using β -diketiminato-stabilized magnesium bases

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Opening-up new synthetic applications of β -diketiminato-stabilized magnesium complexes, this case study compares the ability of the alkyl $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}\text{Mg}(\text{Bu})(\text{THF})]$ (1) and the amido reagent $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}\text{Mg}(\text{TMP})]$ (2) ($\text{Ar}^* = 2,6\text{-}i\text{-Pr}_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_3$) to promote direct Mg–H exchange towards the series of 1,3-benzoazoles: benzoxazole (boz), benzothiazole (btz) and *N*-methylbenzimidazole (blm^{Me}). Both reagents deprotonate boz at room temperature to yield $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}\text{Mg}\{\text{O}(\text{o-C}_6\text{H}_4)\text{NC}\}(\text{THF})]$ (3) via the C–O bond cleavage of a putative C2-magnesiated-benzoxazolyl intermediate. Structurally tracking the reactivity of 1 and 2 towards less acidic btz and blm^{Me} showed that the behaviour of reagents 1 and 2 diverged dramatically. Kinetically activated TMP-reagent 2 effectively promotes the deprotonative magnesiation of btz and blm^{Me} under mild reaction conditions, giving the α -metallated intermediates $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}_2\text{Mg}_2\{\text{btz}^*\}_2]$ (4) and $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}_2\text{Mg}_2\{\text{blm}^{\text{Me}*}\}_2]$ (7) ($\text{btz}^* \frac{1}{4}$ 2-benzothiazolyl; $\text{blm}^{\text{Me}*} \frac{1}{4}$ 2-*N*-methylbenzimidazolyl). Analysis of crystallographic and NMR data revealed that in 4 and 7 the metallated carbon atoms display a markedly carbenic character and that in solution these species exist at room temperature solely as the ring-closed products, without any observable equilibration to the acyclic isomers. Contrastingly, alkyl reagent 1 decreases the magnesiation rate of btz facilitating an intriguing new cascade activation process of two molecules of substrate involving a sequence of deprotonation/coordination/C–C coupling and ring-opening reactions to yield $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}\text{Mg}\{(\text{btz}^*)\text{C}(\text{H})=\text{N}(\text{o-C}_6\text{H}_4)\text{S}\}]$ (5). Hydrolysis of 5 followed by addition of the radical oxidant TEMPO ultimately produces the homocoupled product bis(benzothiazole) 6 in a 72% isolated yield. Thus, this establishes a novel transition-metal-free method to prepare homocoupled thiazoles. More straightforwardly, the coordination product $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}\text{Mg}(\text{Bu})(\text{blm}^{\text{Me}})]$ (8) was obtained when equimolar amounts of blm^{Me} and 1 were reacted, illustrating the kinetic stubbornness of the Mg–C bond in butyl derivative 1. Complex 8 can be envisaged as a valuable guide to the constitution of a premetallation complex (in relation to the complex-induced proximity effect, CIPE).

Introduction

Advances in the preparation of magnesium compounds supported on sterically highly demanding β -diketiminato ligands¹ have been key for recent breakthroughs in synthesis. Acting as steric stabilizers, facilitating the formation of robust six-membered metalacycles, the use of these ligands has enabled

the isolation of the first compounds exhibiting Mg–Mg metal–metal bonds² as well as trapping a record high nuclearity $\{\text{Mg}_8\text{H}_{10}\}^{6+}$ hydride cluster which shows complete hydrogen desorption at 200 °C, an exceptionally low temperature for a molecular magnesium hydride complex.³ Within the context of their catalytic applications, magnesium β -diketiminato complexes have proved to be extremely active single-site initiators for the polymerisation of *rac*-lactide;⁴ whereas pioneering work by Hill *et al.* has shown that magnesium alkyl compounds bearing these ligands can be efficient precatalysts for intramolecular hydroamination reactions of a wide range of aminoalkenes.⁵ Furthermore the extension of this chemistry to magnesium's heavier congeners calcium, strontium and

barium has led to the development of novel catalytic systems for a myriad of reactions such as hydrogenation of alkenes,⁶ hydrosilation of ketones,⁷ hydroamination of vinylarenes,⁸ carbodiimides⁹ and isocyanates¹⁰ to name but a few.

Despite the increasing interest in the synthetic applications of this important family of magnesium compounds, their potential use as metalating reagents capable of promoting direct Mg–H exchange reactions of organic molecules has not yet been investigated. This is even more surprising taking into account that magnesium reagents, in particular magnesium amides, have found employment as efficient alternatives to more traditional lithium-based metalating reagents such as LDA or LiTMP (DA = diisopropylamide, TMP = 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidide) for executing deprotonation reactions of aromatic and heteroaromatic molecules as a prerequisite to tandem bond-forming approaches,¹¹ offering improved regioselectivities and allowing the use of milder reaction conditions¹² (due largely to the *in situ* formation of more stable organomagnesium intermediate species). Furthermore, the metalating power of these magnesium compounds can be greatly boosted by combining them with alkali-metal reagents. Major contributors to this area are Knochen's Turbo Hauser bases (*e.g.* TMPMgCl·LiCl) which, in exhibiting an enhanced functional group tolerance allow access to regioselective functionalised aryl, heteroaryl and metallocenyl compounds,¹³ and Mulvey's heterobimetallic amide systems (*e.g.* [NaMg(TMP)₂R], R $\frac{1}{4}$ Bu, CH₂SiMe₃) that are able to perform the direct magnesiation¹⁴ of molecules that usually are inert towards conventional organomagnesium reagents, such as benzene,¹⁵ toluene¹⁶ or ferrocene¹⁷ amongst many others. Building on these important precedents, in this manuscript we report our findings on assessing the metalating performance of two well-defined b-

diketiminato-supported magnesium alkyl and amido compounds towards the homologous series of 1,3-benzoozoles: benzoxazole (boz), benzothiazole (btz) and *N*-methyl benzimidazole (bIm^{Me}).

Members of the important family of 1,3-azoles, these molecules are precious structural units present in many pharmaceuticals, natural products, functional materials and many other biologically active molecules.¹⁸ One of the most versatile and direct synthetic tools used to functionalize these heterocycles, enabling their introduction into more complex molecular scaffolds, is deprotonative metalation.¹⁹ Thus, in general, 1,3-azoles can be readily metalated at their most acidic C2 position²⁰ by a wide range of organometallic reagents which span from traditional homometallic bases such as organolithium and organomagnesium compounds²¹ to more sophisticated ate complexes such as magnesiates²² or zincates.²³ However, in some cases complications can be encountered due to the lack of stability of the generated metalated intermediate, which, depending on the reaction conditions and the organometallic source employed, can be in equilibrium with its isocyano tautomer II, resulting from the ring opening of I (Fig. 1).²⁴ Thus, for example, attempts to trap 2-lithioxazoles with electrophiles usually afford mixtures of the products of substitution at the C2 and C4 position (resulting from the reaction of the ring-open enolate form II with the electrophile followed by its cyclization) even when the reactions are performed at -78 °C.²⁵

Fig. 1 Equilibrium between C2-metalated 1,3-azoles and their ring-opened isomers.

NMR spectroscopic and X-ray crystallographic structural studies have shown that metalated thiazoles and imidazoles tend to be more stable than oxazoles, with the equilibrium depicted in Fig. 1 lying mainly towards the cyclic isomers I.²⁶ As a consequence, benzothiazole, for example, can be readily C2 deprotonated without ring opening using magnesium-based reagents such as Turbo-Hauser bases (Scheme 1a)^{13a} or Grignard reagents. A noteworthy specific example is the magnesiation of btz by EtMgCl which is a key step in the large-scale synthesis of argininy]benzo[*d*]thiazole (an intermediate to the tryptase inhibitor RWJ-56423).^{21d} Notwithstanding, contrasting with these relatively straightforward methodologies, we have recently found that, magnesium compounds supported by the highly sterically demanding bis(amido) ligand {Ph₂Si(NAr*)₂}²⁻ (Ar* $\frac{1}{4}$ 2,6-*i*-Pr₂-C₆H₃) can initiate an unstoppable cascade of reactions which involve direct magnesiation, C–C coupling, ring opening, nucleophilic addition and intramolecular deprotonation of three molecules of btz at room temperature, revealing a novel type of main-group-mediated-*N*-heterocycle activation.²⁷ Initial studies show that the bulky bis(amido)ligand, rather than acting merely as a steric stabilizer, plays a more sophisticated role promoting this sequence of fast intramolecular reactions.

Gripped by these initial intriguing findings, in this manuscript, we extend our studies to the b-diketiminato magnesium complexes [{Ar*NC(Me)CHC(Me)NAr*}Mg(Bu)(THF)] (1) and [{Ar*NC(Me)CHC(Me)NAr*}Mg(TMP)] (2) (Ar* = 2,6-*i*-Pr₂-C₆H₃), investigating specifically (i) their metalating power towards promoting direct magnesiations of this important family of heterocycles; (ii) their ability to stabilize and facilitate the entrapment of sensitive anions, and (iii) their capacity to promote sequential C–H, C–C, and C–X bond activations of 1,3-benzoozoles within reaction cascade processes.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of β -diketiminato magnesium bases

Our studies commenced by reacting equimolar amounts of Ar*N]C(Me)CH]C(Me)NHAr* (nacnacH)²⁸ with MgBu₂ or Mg(TMP)₂²⁹ which led to the isolation of the β -diketiminato

Scheme 1 Synthesis of β -diketiminato magnesium complexes 1 and 2.

magnesium complexes $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}\text{Mg}(\text{Bu})(\text{THF})]$ (1) or $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}\text{Mg}(\text{TMP})]$ (2) as colourless crystals in 54% and 52% yields respectively.³⁰ In the case of 1 a solvent mixture of hexane–THF was employed, whereas for the formation of 2 the reaction mixture had to be refluxed in hexane for 1 hour to ensure that the reaction went to completion (Scheme 1, see ESI† for experimental details). Contrasting with previous examples reported in the literature to prepare b-diketimate magnesium amides,³¹ we find that compound 2 cannot be obtained by the alternative method of treating butyl compound 1 with the amine TMP(H), even under forcing refluxing conditions. This can be attributed to the larger steric constraints imposed by this highly branched cyclic amine in comparison with the amines employed in these previous studies.³¹

Heteroleptic compounds 1 and 2 were characterized in solution using ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy (see ESI† for details) and their molecular structures in the solid state were determined using X-ray diffraction (Fig. S1† and Fig. 2 respectively). Butyl complex 1 exhibits a structure similar to those previously reported for monomeric b-diketimate magnesium alkyl species,³² displaying a distorted tetrahedral Mg centre bonded to the chelating nacnac ligand, a terminal butyl group and a molecule of THF.³³

Contrastingly, in the also monomeric TMP-complex 2, Mg adopts a distorted trigonal planar geometry $[\Sigma\text{Mg} = 360^\circ]$ by binding to three N atoms, two of them provided by the b-diketimate ligand and a third one from the amide TMP.³⁴ Surprisingly, despite the numerous applications that TMP-based magnesium reagents have in organic synthesis, in particular within the area of deprotonative metallation, as far as we can ascertain, 2 represents the first example of a b-diketimate complex containing this utility amido functionality, not only of magnesium but indeed of any metal. Highlighting the large steric demands of the TMP ligand, a comparison of the bond angles around Mg indicates that those involving the nitrogen atom of this amido group $[\text{N}2\text{--Mg--N}3, 134.97(6)^\circ; \text{N}1\text{--Mg--N}3, 131.18(6)^\circ]$ are considerably more obtuse than the bite angle of the bidentate nacnac ligand $[\text{N}1\text{--Mg--N}2, 93.85(5)^\circ]$. In addition, it is noteworthy that TMP binds terminally to Mg since this can greatly affect the metalating ability of this compound. The importance of this terminal bonding mode has recently

been highlighted by Mulvey *et al.* as one of the critical aspects of the enhanced magnesiating power exhibited by Knochel's Turbo Hauser base $\text{TMPMgCl}\cdot\text{LiCl}$, since only one Mg–N bond needs to be broken to release the active base.^{35,36}

Deprotonation of benzoxazole

To probe the ability of 1 and 2 to act as bases towards 1,3-benzoxazoles, we first investigated their reactions with the parent benzoxazole whose hydrogen atom at the C2 position is substantially more acidic, in pK_a terms, than those present in benzothiazole or *N*-methylbenzomidazole.³⁷ The room temperature 1 : 1 reactions generated in each case a bright orange solution which deposited a crop of yellow crystals of $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}\text{Mg}\{\text{O}(\text{o-C}_6\text{H}_4)\text{NC}\}(\text{THF})]$ (3) in an average isolated yield of 55% (Scheme 2).³⁸

X-ray crystallographic studies of 3 revealed the presence of an α -(isocyano)phenolate ligand, resulting from the direct magnesiation of boz by 2 followed by a ring-opening reaction, which binds terminally to Mg through its oxygen atom (Fig. 3). The b-diketimate ligand and a molecule of THF complete the molecular structure of 3 giving Mg a distorted tetrahedral geometry overall. Although previous deprotonation studies of boz using the mixed-metal base LiMgBu_3 generated *in situ* have proposed, on the basis of NMR analysis, that at room temperature the resulting 2-benzoxazolyl intermediate quickly isomerizes to its open α -(isocyano)phenolate form,²² 3 is to the best of our knowledge the first structurally defined intermediate of direct magnesiation of a 1,3-benzoxazole ^1H and ^{13}C NMR studies using deuterated THF as a solvent indicated that in solution 3 retains its solid-state structure, without observing equilibration to its ring-closed isomer. This is mostly evidenced by the presence in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum of three distinct resonances at 164.71, 162.15 and 118.02 ppm which can be

Scheme 2 Reactivity of boz with compounds 1 and 2.

Fig. 2 Molecular structure of 2 with 50% probability displacement ellipsoids. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

Fig. 3 Molecular structure of 3 with 50% probability displacement ellipsoids. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

assigned to the isocyanide, a-C and b-C of the phenolate group. It should be noted that NMR analysis of reaction mixtures of 2 (or 1) with btz showed only the presence of 3 in solution, even when the spectra were recorded at low temperatures ($-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), suggesting that once the metalation has taken place, the cyclic intermediate (Fig. 1), whose presence cannot be detected, rapidly undergoes complete ring opening to form acyclic 3. Seminal NMR spectroscopy and X-ray crystallographic structural studies by Boche have shown that lithiated oxazoles exist in solution (even at temperatures as low as $-105\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) as their acyclic isomers. This can be rationalized in terms of the high oxophilic character of highly polar Li which should facilitate the cleavage of the C2–O bond.²⁶ Supporting this hypothesis, the *in situ* transmetalation of these intermediates with ZnCl_2 leads to the formation of the relevant ring-closed zincated species (favoured by the significantly less polar and therefore more covalent character of the newly generated Zn–C bond),^{26,39} which can then be subsequently exploited in organic transformations such as Negishi cross-coupling reactions.^{40,41}

In view of these results, our studies suggest that magnesiated benzoxazole behaves in a similar manner to its lithiated congener. Thus the marked affinity of Mg for coordination to an oxygen anion appears to dictate the final outcome of the reaction favouring the formation of α -(isocyano)phenolate complex 3. Furthermore the presence of the sterically highly demanding b-diketiminato ligand does not seem to have a measurable effect on the position of the equilibrium between the open and closed forms of this magnesiated benzoxazole, which lies exclusively on the side of the acyclic isomer even at lower temperatures with 3 being the only species that can be detected in solution.

Deprotonation of benzothiazole: magnesiation *versus* cascade activation

We next turned our attention to the sulphur congener btz, for which selective C2-metallation has been previously reported using magnesium-based reagents,^{21,22} although no structural authentication of the metalated intermediates involved has yet been forthcoming. Bearing in mind that, in general, magnesium amides exhibit an enhanced kinetic basicity compared to related magnesium alkyl compounds,¹² we first studied the reactivity of TMP derivative 2 towards btz. The room-temperature 1 : 1 reaction in THF solution formed a deep red solution which deposited a crop of red crystals of $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}_2\text{Mg}_2\{\text{btz}^*\}_2]$ (4) ($\text{btz}^* \frac{1}{4}$ 2-benzothiazolyl) in an isolated yield of 43% (Scheme 3).³⁸

The centrosymmetric dimeric molecular structure of 4 (Fig. 4) confirmed the C2 magnesiation of btz has taken place by featuring two $\{(\beta\text{-diketiminato})\text{Mg}\}$ fragments connected by two bridging benzothiazolyl (btz^*) anions, which act as asymmetric bridges through their metalated carbon and nitrogen atoms (C7 and N1). This distinct coordination mode of the newly formed btz^* groups gives rise to the closure of a novel six-membered $\{\text{MgCNMgCN}\}$ ring, which shares each Mg vertex with six-membered metalacycles resulting from the chelating coordination of the nacnac ligand to Mg. The distorted tetrahedral geometry around Mg [bond angles ranging from $93.17(7)$ to

Scheme 3 Reactivity of btz with compounds 1 and 2.

Fig. 4 Molecular structure of 4 with 50% probability displacement ellipsoids. Hydrogen atoms and hexane solvent molecule are omitted for clarity.

$117.87(8)^{\circ}$; mean, 109.56°) denotes an approximately orthogonal disposition of these three fused six-membered rings. A close inspection of the Mg–N1 [$2.097(2)\text{ \AA}$] and Mg–C7 [$2.193(2)\text{ \AA}$] bond distances in 4 shows that, while the former is considerably shorter than other Mg–N values reported for related b-diketiminato-Mg compounds containing neutral nitrogen donors such as pyridine or picoline [e.g. $2.174(3)$ and $2.213(4)\text{ \AA}$],⁴² the latter is slightly elongated compared to that in aryl compound $[(\text{NacNac})\text{Mg}(\text{Ph})(\text{OEt}_2)]$ [$2.139(3)\text{ \AA}$] which also contains a *pseudo*-tetrahedral Mg bonded to an sp^2 hybridized carbon.^{31a} This coupled with the moderate but noticeable elongation of the N1–C7 and S–C7 bond distances and widening of the N1–C7–S bond angle of the btz^* rings [$1.330(3)$, $1.743(2)\text{ \AA}$ and $110.57(15)^{\circ}$ respectively] when compared with the values found in free benzothiazole [$1.2979(15)$, $1.7222(13)\text{ \AA}$ and $116.28(9)^{\circ}$],⁴³ suggests that 4 can alternatively be described as a 3-(magnesium β -diketiminato)benzothiazol-2-ylidene dimer. In this regard, the structures of related lithiated and zincated thiazole compounds have been instructively described by Boche as [3-metallo-thiazol-2-ylidenes] by close comparison of the structural differences between these species and their parent thiazole molecules and those found between thiazolium salts and a thiazol-2-ylidene compound.^{44,45} Consistent with this

alternative description of 4, its Mg–C distance [2.193(2) Å] is close to those witnessed in Mg–N-heterocyclic carbene adducts [ranging from 2.200(2) to 2.288(5) Å],^{36,46} whereas its Mg–N7 bond [2.097(2) Å] is just marginally longer than the other two remaining Mg–N_{nacnac} bonds present in the molecule [2.0587(19) and 2.0696(18) Å].

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopic investigations revealed that the solid-state structure of 4 appears to be retained at room temperature in deuterated benzene solutions.⁴⁷ The most diagnostic resonance in the ¹³C NMR spectrum appears at 216.29 ppm for the C2 carbon of the btz* group. Showing a large downfield shift when compared with the C2 resonance observed in parent btz (δ ¼ 154.07 ppm), this signal is much closer to that observed for free 3-(2,6-diisopropylphenyl)-4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-ylidene (δ ¼ 254.2 ppm),⁴⁸ reflecting the moderate carbenic character of this C as previously discussed for the X-ray crystallographic studies and more importantly, characteristic of a ring-closed structure for the metalated benzothiazole groups in solution. Remarkably, both ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of 4 at room temperature displayed well-resolved sharp signals, and with no detectable resonances attributable to a ring-open α-(isocyano)phenylthiolate derivative (similar to 3). This contrasts with previous solution studies for lithiated benzothiazole and 4,5-dimethylthiazole which show that even at lower temperatures (-35 °C), both ring-opened and a ring-closed species coexist in solution.^{26a} The remarkable room-temperature solution stability of 4 is all the more surprising when considering that although metallated thiazoles have a much less pronounced tendency to undergo ring-opening than their parent oxazole derivatives,²⁶ most of the reported synthetic procedures that involve the deprotonation of these heterocycles employing polar organolithium or organomagnesium reagents require the use of sub-ambient temperatures, suggesting that the presence of the sterically demanding b-diketimate ligands present in 4 coupled with its rigid tricyclic dimeric structure must play an important role in conferring an enhanced stability to the newly generated Mg–C_{btz*} bonds, minimizing the competing ring-opening process. The stabilizing role of the b-diketimate ligand is in sharp contrast with our previous studies using magnesium reagents supported on a different type of sterically highly demanding ligand, namely dianionic bis(amido) {Ph₂Si(NAr*)₂}²⁻ (Ar* ¼ 2,6-*i*-Pr₂-C₆H₃) where the initial deprotonation of btz induces a cascade of reactions in which the bis(amide) itself acts as a base.²⁷

Encouraged by the efficient and selective magnesiation ability of 2 towards btz as well as the fact that conventional Grignard reagents can deprotonate this heterocycle at 0 °C,^{21d} we next decided to investigate the reactivity of the butyl magnesium b-diketimate 1. Thus, the addition of one molar equivalent of btz to a solution of 1 in THF at room temperature is accompanied by a yellow to deep blue colour change. Freezer cooling of this solution afforded blue crystals of [{Ar*NC(Me)-CHC(Me)NAr*}Mg{(btz*)C(H)N(2-C₆H₄-1-S)}] (5) (btz* ¼ 2-benzothiazolyl) (in an isolated yield of 23%,⁴⁹ Scheme 3) as

determined by solution NMR spectroscopy and X-ray crystallography.

Contrasting to the situation for 4, X-ray crystallographic studies of 5 (Fig. 5)⁵⁰ unveiled the presence of a new mono-anionic ligand resulting from the activation of two molecules of btz with a negative charge localized on one of the sulfur atoms (S1). From its constitution, it appears that one molecule of btz has been deprotonated, whereas the other one, retaining its hydrogen atom, undergoes ring-opening. Coordinating to Mg in a k³-S, N, N fashion (involving S1, N1 and N2, Fig. 5), this new ligand can be envisaged as a phenyl-thiolate-tethered 1,4-butadiene with one of its N]C units being part of the btz* ring. This tridentate coordination mode allows the formation of two five-membered rings fused through the Mg–N1 bond [2.211(3) Å], giving rise overall to a 6-5-5-5-6 fused ring system.

All the anticipated distinct hydrogen atoms for this new anionic ligand are accounted for and well resolved in the ¹H NMR spectrum of 5 in C₆D₆ solutions and they can be assigned by combination of ¹H-¹H COSY and ¹H-¹³C HSQC experiments (see ESI† for full details).⁵¹

A plausible explanation for the formation of 5 is depicted in Scheme 4. At room temperature butyl-base 1 can magnesiate btz, though this reaction must be significantly slower than when TMP-base 2 is employed, as it involves the cleavage of a kinetically more stubborn Mg–C_{Bu} bond.⁵² This retardation translates into the formation of some b-diketimate Mg–btz* species which will coexist in the solution with some unreacted btz molecules. This scenario switches on an alternative reaction pathway for the remaining free btz, which can coordinate as a neutral N-donor ligand to the Mg center (akin to the role of THF in 1) of the benzothiazolyl species (step a, Scheme 4),^{53,54} facilitating its intramolecular nucleophilic attack at the C2 position by the btz* anion which generates a new C–C bond with concomitant dearomatization of the btz molecule (step b, Scheme 4). This proposed intermediate can then undergo ring-opening of the non-aromatic ring through cleavage of its C–S bond (step c, Scheme 4) to form 5 as the final product of the reaction. This proposed cascade process is supported by ¹H NMR monitoring studies of the reaction of isolated crystals of benzothiazolyl species 4 with one molar equivalent of btz in deuterated benzene which revealed the instantaneous formation of 5 (Scheme 3), suggesting that the reaction rate of the magnesiation step is the key to enable this alternative domino of intramolecular reactions.

Fig. 5 Molecular structure of 5 with 50% probability displacement ellipsoids. Hydrogen atoms and THF molecules of crystallization are omitted for clarity.

Scheme 4 Proposed mechanism for the formation of 5.

To elaborate, using the kinetically activated TMP-base 2, the deprotonation of btz occurs very rapidly, and therefore the use of equimolar amounts of the starting materials leads to the isolation of the stable benzothiazolyl compound 4. Alternatively, when an excess of btz is employed (2 molar equivalents), a situation mimicking that when equimolar amounts of butyl compound 1 and btz are confronted is recreated. That is to say, the presence in solution of Mg-benzothiazolyl units with free btz can then follow the reaction pathway postulated in Scheme 4.

Furthermore, as above mentioned, we have recently reported that treatment of btz with sodium-magnesiate $[\{Na(THF)_6\}^+ \{ (Ph_2Si(NAr^*)_2)Mg(Bu)(THF) \}^-]$ leads to a novel magnesium-mediated cascade activation of three molecules of this heterocycle.²⁷ Although this case is a more complex process, with more steps involved, the initial three steps of the cascade mechanism proposed match those in the formation of 5. Thus, by using the b-diketimate-stabilized magnesium complexes 1 or 2, new light has been shed on the constitution of the putative intermediates involved in these novel room-temperature cascade activations of btz where the initial magnesiation initiates a domino reaction of C–C coupling of the heterocyclic rings and ring-opening. In addition, these results not only provide further support for the mechanism proposed earlier but also highlight the wider generality of this type of process. Although this type of activation is unprecedented in magnesium chemistry, these results seem more related to the reactivity exhibited by d^0f^n metal alkyl complexes ($M \frac{1}{4} Sc, Y, Lu$ or U) supported by a 1,1⁰-ferrocenylene bis(amide) ligand which can promote ring opening reactions of methyl-imidazole, involving C–H activation of the heterocycle, followed by C–C coupling reactions.⁵⁵ This non-obvious parallelism between the chemistry of lanthanides and alkali-earth metal complexes has been recently noted by Hill *et al.* within the context of group 2-catalysed hydroamination and hydrophosphination of unsaturated organic electrophiles.⁵

Hydrolysis of 5 (which can be easily prepared *in situ* by reaction of 1 with 2 molar equivalents of btz) afforded 2,3-dihydro-2,2'-bis(benzothiazole) which can be readily oxidized by

treatment with radical oxidant TEMPO [(2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidin-1-yl)oxyl]⁵⁶ furnishing 2,2'-bis(benzothiazole) 6 in a 72% isolated yield (Scheme 5). This novel, atom-efficient, synthetic route to prepare 6 under mild reaction conditions (room temperature, stoichiometric amount of Mg base, short reaction times) contrasts with previous transition-metal-catalysed C–C bond formation approaches involving direct C–H azole activation which usually require longer reaction times (12–24 hours) and higher temperatures (140 °C).⁵⁷ Closely related to this work, Daugulis has reported the transition-metal-catalysed deprotonative dimerization of azoles using a variety of first row transition-metal salts such as $MnCl_2$, $FeCl_3$, $CoCl_2$, $NiCl_2$ or $CuCl_2$ as catalysts, employing the Turbo Hauser reagent $TMPMgClLiCl$ ¹³ as a base and oxygen as a terminal oxidant.⁵⁸ Although the mechanisms involved in these transformations are not fully understood, Cahiez has proposed for $MnCl_2$ -catalysed homocoupling reactions of Grignard reagents that initially the transmetalation of the relevant aryl (or heteroaryl) group from magnesium to manganese takes place, forming a bis(aryl) manganese intermediate which in turn can react with oxygen to generate a more reactive Mn(IV) species which can rapidly undergo reductive elimination to yield the desired homocoupled product.⁵⁹

In marked contrast to these methodologies, here we disclose a transition-metal-free feasible approach for the synthesis of bis(thiazoles) by using magnesium bases 1 or 2 in the presence of a 2 molar excess of btz where the isolation and structural characterization of intermediates 4 and 5 provide essential clues that help to rationalize the formation of bis(benzothiazole) 6.⁶⁰ Thus, this method is based on a novel sequential magnesiation/C–C coupling/ring-opening cascade process to yield 5 which in turn can be easily hydrolyzed and oxidized in a final step to produce 6, which facilitates the ring-closure and re-aromatization of the btz molecule that has previously undergone ring opening.

Deprotonation of *N*-methyl benzimidazole: magnesiation vs. coordination

To conclude this comparative study, the reactions of magnesium bases 1 and 2 with *N*-methyl benzimidazole (bIm^{Me}) were also probed. Interestingly, it should be noted that despite the limited information available on the real constitution of C2-metallated imidazoles, recent studies in d-block chemistry have

Scheme 5 Magnesium-mediated homocoupling reaction of benzothiazole.

revealed that the deprotonation of these heterocycles when coordinated to transition metal complexes followed by electrophilic interception has led to the isolation of novel NHC complexes and well as the disclosure of activation processes involving C–N cleavage of other *N*-heterocyclic molecules such as imidazoles and bipyridines.⁶¹

Our studies show contrasting reactivities for compounds 1 and 2. Thus while the TMP-base 2 is capable of promoting the direct magnesiation of bIm^{Me} at the C2 position to generate $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}_2\text{Mg}_2\{\text{bIm}^{\text{Me}*}\}_2]$ (7) whose constitution has a strong resemblance to that of btz metalation product 4, the butyl derivative 1 is inert towards the reaction, even under refluxing conditions, leading to the isolation of bIm^{Me} adduct $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}\text{Mg}(\text{Bu})(\text{bIm}^{\text{Me}})]$ (8), resulting from the substitution of the THF molecule coordinated to Mg in 1 by a molecule of bIm^{Me} (Scheme 6). Compounds 7 and 8 can be isolated as crystalline solids in 57 and 43% yields respectively and characterized by X-ray crystallography and NMR spectroscopic techniques.

While structural analysis of 7 was complicated by disordered hexane solvent molecules and by generally weak diffraction intensities, after multiple attempts the model shown in Fig. 6 was obtained and this unambiguously shows the atomic connectivity and other essential structural features. Similarly to 4, dinuclear 7 displays a centrosymmetric structure comprising two $\{(\text{b-diketimate})\text{Mg}\}$ fragments where the Mg atoms are doubly bridged by two anionic 2-*N*-methylbenzimidazolyl ($\text{bIm}^{\text{Me}*}$) ligands, which coordinate asymmetrically through one of their nitrogen atoms and the carbon that has experienced the deprotonation (N3 and C30 respectively in Fig. 6), forming a $\{\text{MgCNMgCN}\}$ six-membered ring. Unfortunately the low precision of this structure precludes a meaningful comparison of its geometrical parameters with those of 4 in order to assess the carbene character of the $\text{bIm}^{\text{Me}*}$ anion present in 7. As far as we can ascertain 7 represents the first structurally defined example of a magnesiation of an *N*-alkyl imidazole molecule. Furthermore, the relatively simple structure of 7 contrasts with the much more complex supramolecular scaffolding displayed by the product of the reaction of 1-methyl-4-*tert*-butylimidazole with methylolithium, which comprises 16 lithium atoms and 8

Fig. 6 Molecular structure of 7 with 50% probability displacement ellipsoids. Hydrogen atoms and a hexane molecule of crystallization are omitted for clarity.

imidazolyl anions combined with 2 oxo and 4 alkoxo ligand anions, with the oxygen-based anions formed as a result of the partial degradation of the ethereal solvents employed in the presence of the lithium alkyl reagent.⁴⁴

Previous NMR studies have revealed that, while 2-lithio-*N*-methyl imidazole stays in d^8 -THF solution exclusively as its ring-closed form at temperatures as high as 60 °C, at room temperature parent 2-lithio-*N*-methyl benzimidazole undergoes partial ring-opening.^{26a} ¹H and ¹³C NMR investigations of 7 in deuterated benzene solutions indicate, that, similarly to 4, its dimeric constitution is retained, without observing an equilibrium with its ring-opened isomer. Thus the ¹³C NMR spectrum of 7 displayed 15 well-resolved resonances in the aromatic region, 8 of which can be assigned to the β -diketimate ligand, while the remaining 7 belong to the $\text{bIm}^{\text{Me}*}$ ring, including an informative signal at 192.93 ppm for the carbon atom that has been magnesiated. Interestingly although this chemical shift compares well with that previously reported for the C2 of an alpha-magnesiated *N*-methyl indole species (181 ppm),⁶² it is also close to that exhibited for the carbene C of the *N*-heterocyclic carbene adduct ${}^n\text{Bu}_s\text{Mg}_4.2\text{IPr}$ (IPr $\frac{1}{4}$ 1,3-bis-(2,6-diisopropylphenyl)imidazol-2-ylidene) (197.3 ppm),³⁶ hinting at a similar carbenic character for 7 to that discussed for 4. Remarkably, when 7 was treated with an extra equivalent of bIm^{Me} no reaction was observed, even when the mixture was heated under reflux for 12 hours which contrasts with the room-temperature activation of btz when one molar equivalent of this heterocycle is added to 4, which leads to isolation of 5 (*vide infra*).

Also diverging from the btz reactivity, when butyl compound 1 is confronted with bIm^{Me} the formation of the adduct $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}\text{Mg}(\text{Bu})(\text{bIm}^{\text{Me}})]$ (8) takes place. X-ray diffraction analysis shows that 8 is isostructural with precursor 1, where now Mg is bonded to a molecule of bIm^{Me} acting as a nitrogen donor (Fig. 7). Although there are other examples in the literature containing *N*-alkyl imidazoles coordinated to Mg centers,⁶³ the closest precedent to 8 is the pyridine (py) complex $[\{\text{Ar}^*\text{NC}(\text{Me})\text{CHC}(\text{Me})\text{NAr}^*\}\text{Mg}(\text{Bu})(\text{py})]$ recently reported by Hill, which in the presence of PhSiH_3 at 60 °C promotes the dearomatization of py by a hydride transfer.⁴² NMR studies of 8 indicate that in C_6D_6 solution bIm^{Me}

Scheme 6 Reactivity of bIm^{Me} with compounds 1 and 2.

Fig. 7 Molecular structure of 8 with 50% probability displacement ellipsoids. Hydrogen atoms, minor disorder components in the Bu group and a hexane molecule of crystallization are omitted for clarity.

remains coordinated to Mg, which translates into a slight (but noticeable) modification of the chemical shifts of its resonances in the ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of 8 compared to those observed for free bIm^{Me} .⁶⁴

Illustrating the kinetic limitations of 1, despite the coordination of bIm^{Me} to Mg which brings the basic butyl group and Ha of bIm^{Me} in close proximity to each other, no magnesiation is observed even under forcing refluxing conditions or by adding one molar equivalent of the amine TMP(H). Drawing a comparison between α -deprotonation of 1,3-benzoxazoles and Directed *ortho*-Metallation (DoM) chemistry,⁶⁵ 8 can be interpreted as a valuable guide to the nature of a premetallation complex for the formation of 7 (in a complex-induced proximity effect, CIPE, sense)⁶⁶ or at least as a key intermediate to support the reaction pathway depicted in Scheme 4, which involves the coordination of a 1,3-benzoxazole (in this case btz) as a neutral 2e-nitrogen donor to a $\{(\text{b-diketiminate})\text{Mg}(\text{heteroaryl})\}$ fragment.

Conclusions

By systematically comparing and structurally mapping the reactions of *b*-diketimate-stabilized magnesium bases 1 and 2 with the series of 1,3-benzo(azoles), boz, btz and bIm^{Me} we provide the first synthetic insights into the ability of these compounds to promote direct magnesiation of this family of *N*-heterocyclic molecules. Possessing the most activated hydrogen (in terms of $\text{p}K_{\text{a}}$ values), boz can be deprotonated at its C2 position by both alkyl 1 and amido 2 affording in each case compound 3 containing an α -(isocyano)phenolate anion resulting from the C–O cleavage of a putative magnesiated-benzoxazolyl intermediate. In contrast, studying the reactions of the less acidic congeners btz and bIm^{Me} , the behaviour of compounds 1 and 2 diverged with dramatic consequences in the final outcome of the reactions. This divergence can be rationalized in terms of the enhanced kinetic basicity of Mg–N bonds *versus* Mg–C bonds. Thus, TMP derivative 2 can successfully promote the room-temperature direct Mg–H exchange reactions of btz and bIm^{Me} leading to the isolation of dimers 4 and 7 respectively. Both compounds exhibit similar structures in the solid state, containing two benzo(azoly)

bridges which coordinate asymmetrically through their metallated C and N atoms to the Mg centers. Analysis of the crystallographic data coupled with NMR studies show that in 4 and 7 the metallated carbons display a markedly carbenic character and that in solution these species exist at room temperature solely as the ring-closed products, without any observable equilibration to the relevant acyclic products. Contrastingly when these reactions were explored using alkyl base 2, btz and bIm^{Me} exhibit markedly different behaviours. The reaction of equimolar amounts of 2 and btz leads to the isolation of 5 which contains a novel monoanionic tridentate ligand resulting from a remarkable room temperature cascade activation process, involving two molecules of btz. By employing the kinetically more retarded butyl base 1 a new reaction scenario is available where some of the newly generated Mg-benzothiazolyl species coexist with some unreacted btz, which initiates a cascade of fast coordination, C–C coupling and ring opening reactions to yield 5. Demonstrating that the deprotonation of btz is the rate-determining step in this process, 5 can also be obtained quantitatively when benzothiazolyl compound 4 is reacted with one additional equivalent of btz. Hydrolysis of 5 followed by radical oxidation with TEMPO furnished bis(benzothiazole) 6 in a 72% yield, disclosing a new feasible approach for the synthesis of bis(thiazoles) by using magnesium base 1 in the presence of a 2 molar excess of the relevant heterocycle which is based on a novel sequential magnesiation/C–C coupling/ring-opening cascade process.

On the other hand, illustrating the kinetic resilience of its Mg–C bond, 1 fails to deprotonate bIm^{Me} , affording the coordination adduct 8 where bIm^{Me} acts as a neutral 2e-donor bonding to Mg through N. Akin to DoM chemistry, 8 can be envisaged as a model α -metalation precomplex (in terms of CIPE). Furthermore its isolation, which demonstrates the ability of 1,3-benzoxazoles to act as Lewis donors for $\{(\text{b-diketiminate})\text{Mg}\}$ fragments, supports the reaction pathway proposed for the cascade activation of btz for the formation of 5.

Collectively these studies disclose the ability of a novel kinetically activated TMP-magnesium base 2 to effectively perform direct Mg–H exchange reactions of the 1,3-benzoxazoles series under mild conditions (room temperature, stoichiometric amounts of reagents, short reaction times). Seemingly critical for the success of these reactions, 2 possesses a terminal basic TMP group and is monomeric due to the bulk of the *b*-diketimate ligand support. Furthermore, our studies suggest that this ligand offers further stabilization to the benzothiazolyl (btz^*) and *N*-methylbenzimidazolyl ($\text{bIm}^{\text{Me}*}$) anions present in 4 and 7 respectively which do not undergo equilibration with their ring-open isomers.

To conclude, by slowing down the rate of the magnesiation reaction of btz, using the kinetically more retarded butyl base 1, we have unveiled a novel magnesium-mediated type of activation leading to the ring opening and functionalization of benzothiazole rings which ultimately enables the isolation of the homocoupled product bis(benzothiazole) 6. These results highlight the potential to apply this novel methodology to other *N*-heterocyclic molecules. This will be explored in our future work.

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